

Exploring Problem Behavior in the Moroccan EFL High School Classroom: Types, Causes, and Coping Strategies

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Abstract:- One of the greatest concerns of teachers, administrators, and parents is the issue of problem behavior at school. In fact, providing a safe, positive and supportive classroom environment allowing students ample opportunities to learn and grow is a top concern for every caring teacher. The objective of this research is to investigate the different common aspects of students' disciplinary problems in Moroccan EFL high school classrooms. More specifically, this article aims at examining the various types and causes of classroom misbehavior as well as the strategies Moroccan teachers use to cope with it. The study involved 69 Moroccan high school teachers and 240 high school students who were selected on the basis of convenient sampling. The qualitative and quantitative data obtained from teachers and students through questionnaires, interviews and classroom observations were analyzed by triangulation. The descriptive analysis yielded the following findings. First, minor disciplinary issues are the most common types of disruptive behavior faced by Moroccan EFL high school teachers. Second, family problems, negative attitudes towards school and teacher behavior are the main causes of student misbehavior. The findings also suggest a number of effective ways for teachers to deal with diverse types of disciplinary problems. The study ends up with some pedagogical implications and suggestions for further research addressing the issue of problem behavior.

Keywords:- Problem behavior; Causes; Strategies; EFL high school;

I. INTRODUCTION

Successful classrooms are oftentimes described as those capable of providing an exciting and dynamic learning experience for everyone involved in the teaching-learning process. Unfortunately, students' problem behavior often interferes with this process. Most high school students are adolescents who go through the most difficult and sensitive stage in their lives, and factors such as family background, self-confidence, and teachers' attitudes can greatly affect the student's behavior in the classroom. Accordingly, a good handling of a student's misbehavior can be efficient, while not reacting to it appropriately can only complicate the situation and lead to more problems.

In fact, classroom discipline plays a decisive role in today's educational system. Teachers feel overwhelmed and weak in handling behavior problems in their classrooms (Barron et al., 2000; Eide & Ronan, 2001). Canter (1997) explains that a simple frown or warning was sufficient to shape up a classroom in the past. However, the situation is not that simple in today's classroom owing to a multitude of changes. As a result of the successive social and political changes, the respect and authority of presidents, police officers, doctors, and even teachers declined dramatically (Stevenson, 2010). That is why it is very important to find practical management techniques to meet the needs of the teachers and the students alike. In order to assist teachers in promoting a positive learning environment for their students, a profound understanding of students' misbehaviors is of overriding importance before effective ways to deal with them can be suggested.

II. UNDERSTANDING PROBLEM BEHAVIOR

A. Definition of Problem Behavior

The term "Problem behavior" has been defined by so many educators, theorists, and scholars who are interested in such a very vague issue. In fact, the problem has been referred to by many different appellations including misbehavior, disruptive behavior, and delinquent behavior (Thomson, 2009). According to Supaporn (2000), problem behavior designates repeated, continuous, and/or multiple student behaviors that hinder the ability of instructors to teach and students to learn. Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines the word "disruptive" as an adjective that means "to throw into disorder", "to break apart", indicates that disruptive behaviors are all kinds of behaviors that can break up the ordinary structure of the classroom and perturb its order. By implication, such behaviors interrupt the usual flow and routine of the classroom and decrease the teacher's ability to teach and the student's ability to learn. These behaviors may cause irritation, anxiety, and annoyance. The word "misbehavior" is also defined as a behavior which gravely interferes with the teaching process and/or seriously upsets the normal running of the school (Supaporn, 2000). Besides, problem behavior refers to any behavior considered as inappropriate for the setting or situation in which it occurs (Charles, 2008). In this study, problem behavior and misbehavior are used synonymously and interchangeably to refer to any kind of behaviors that violate the explicit rules or the implicit norms of the classroom, that interfere with the classroom order and that interrupt the process of teaching and learning (Dalgic & Bayhan, 2014).

B. Types of disciplinary problems

Disciplinary problems have been categorized in different ways. In their study, Burgaz and Ekinçi (2016) classified students' misbehaviors in the classroom into three major categories:

- **Minor disciplinary problems:** This is the mild sort of misbehavior occurring in students who are impulsive and act without thinking about the consequences of their actions. They do not think; they “just do it”. Their behaviors are trivial but very frequent. Examples of this type are: excessive talking, chewing gum, avoiding work, coming to class late, getting out of seat without permission, annoying other students, coming unprepared for class, laughing, questioning the teacher's knowledge, clowning, writing on desks, mutilate equipment, marring walls, playing with objects, missing class for countless reasons, not participating in class, playing with electronic gadgets like cell phones, to name but a few. In general, this type includes behaviors which can be irritating or unpleasant but not serious.
- **Serious disciplinary problems:** This is a deliberate, mischievous behavior that is usually planned and less frequent than impulsive behavior. Students who show this kind of behavior are aware of the consequences but do it to fulfill their attention related needs. Examples of this type may include cursing or assaulting another student, talking back to the teacher, making unnecessary noises, cheating, stealing other students' properties, defiance or hostility towards the teacher, fighting with another student, taking pictures while the teacher is writing on the board, teasing other students, threatening other students, and bullying other students. This category consists of behaviors where there may be some physical danger to individuals. Providing these students with the potential consequences of their actions and giving appropriate attention will usually suffice to rectify this behavior.
- **Severe disciplinary problems:** This sort of behavior is usually serious but does not happen often. It is irrational and comes from a student who has self-control problems. This type denotes behaviors like possessing drugs or weapons, breaking classroom properties, lighting a fire in a classroom, assaulting the teacher, physical aggression toward the teacher, bringing insects to class, throwing objects on the teacher or on other students...etc. This type includes behaviors which are very destructive or dangerous to the safety of individuals.

C. Reasons for students' misbehavior in the classroom

When a discipline problem arises, it is important to identify why students are misbehaving. Understanding why they are acting as they are will help the teacher handle the misbehavior and change it or even eradicate it altogether. Of course, sometimes students seem to misbehave for no reason, but most of the time teachers can discover the cause. Shammadh and Anzari (2019) state that a “child's behavior is motivated by unique experiences and the influence of outside forces acting on self-interests. A child's ability to cope with these outside forces may be hampered by abuse,

psychological trauma, physical challenges or neglected needs. When these needs are not met, problems are likely to arise” (p.15). In his paper *A Theory of Human Motivation*, the American psychologist Abraham Maslow (1943) studies how needs and development are interdependent in every person. He explores a hierarchical list of needs that are present in every human. According to Maslow, every person has basic needs that must be met for that person to progress to higher needs and arrive at the top of his/her “Hierarchy of Needs”. This theory brings us face to face with the ultimate cause of misbehavior in the classroom. These needs can be expressed in terms of five basic steps. Step one, the most basic needs, are biological such as food, air, water, and sleep. The next step is the need for safety, which includes security, structure, morality, and health. These two steps in the hierarchy are the basic needs that must be met by society and the family and cannot be efficiently met by educational institutions. After meeting these two basic needs, a person can now progress to the third stage in Maslow's hierarchy; namely, that of love and belonging. As a child progresses through early development, these three areas of need play a very important role in preparing the mind for learning and must be constantly maintained and stimulated. At this point in Maslow's Hierarchy, a child can reach the fourth step, which is Self-esteem. Self-esteem can come from many sources. It includes feelings such as confidence, achievement, respect for others, and respect by others. It is at this stage that the child begins to go beyond their surroundings to look for knowledge. Seeking knowledge can be the missing factor in a child's development. Transcendence is the last step in the hierarchy and is the point at which we seek a better world for others and for ourselves. Teachers' influence is critical in moving students towards this direction. Therefore, students who misbehave in classrooms may experience a breakdown in the first four basic needs. Additionally, continuous exposure to violence, drugs, alcohol, vulgar language, and destructive behavior in the media and the internet are considered direct sources of misbehavior (Sibel et al., 2010). Therefore, if poor behavior is continuously modeled in every corner of society, there will be no end to the problems created for students in schools.

- **Causes originating within the student:** Students' misbehaviors in the classroom can be affected by their social and psychological backgrounds. For instance, social factors such as home background can play a major role in shaping students' behaviors. According to Ding et al. (2008), “the pupil's family can seep negatively into the classroom” (p. 8). This implies that a large part of a student's behavior in the classroom is mainly determined by their home background such as family, home, divorce ... Moreover, students' peer and group relationships also affect their behavior. Students always seek to build up relationships outside home boundaries. These relationships have a great impact on their behavior either positively or negatively. In addition, other psychological factors may be the cause of students' misbehavior. For instance, students may suffer from personal problems, self-concept, inability to handle frustration, seeking of attention, feeling of

rejection, lack of confidence, and feeling of discouragement. Furthermore, another important factor affecting misbehavior is students' attitudes. Indeed, students who perform well in the classroom will develop positive feelings about their school, and will tend to work hard and be cooperative with their peers and teachers. On the contrary, students who perform badly in the classroom will come to develop negative emotions and attitudes towards the school as a whole.

In the same vein, Shamnadh and Anzari (2019) identified the most common cause of misbehavior in the classroom as "attention-Seeking". In fact, adult attention is necessary to children because it is through this attention that they obtain satisfaction of their physical needs and thus, feel significant and develop a kind of self-esteem. Although the attention they obtain through disruptive behavior may be an angry attention, it is more acceptable to them and therefore more reinforcing than being ignored. Through this reinforcement, this disruptive behavior becomes an established part of their behavioral pattern. Students who do not receive enough teacher approval and praise may be further conditioned into believing that the only way they can attract attention is by making trouble for others. The student's behavior, in this case, is not necessarily a deliberate attempt to create problems for the teacher and other students, but a conditioned response associated with the need for attention. Sometimes students do not seek attention from the teacher, but from the other students. This kind of students; or rather troublemakers may have found themselves to be unpopular in class, and have discovered that the way to obtain a measure of acceptance is to raise a laugh at the teacher's expense, or to show themselves to be "tough" or "courageous" by disobeying the teacher (Shamnadh & Anzari, 2019).

- **Causes originating with the teacher:** The teacher's behavior and attitude are also important factors which can have a major effect on the classroom atmosphere as well as on students' behaviors in many ways. First, as Harmer (1991) believes, disciplinary problems may stem from students' reactions to their teachers' behavior. Harmer (1991) states that teachers' informal language, aggressive behavior or negative attitudes lead to students' disrespect for them. Consequently, misbehavior is a normal reaction from students. Second, teachers who are not competent enough are likely to face disciplinary problems in their classrooms. Contrarily, students tend to appreciate, respect, and obey competent teachers. Third, poor planning and coming to school unprepared and improvising lessons, make the teacher liable to encounter disciplinary problems related to classroom management. A good and adequate planning is the appropriate solution. Moreover, a non-punctual teacher does not gain their students appreciation and respect. As a result, disruptive behavior is likely to emerge. Besides, teachers should avoid showing preferences, favorites, favoritism, and bias. Instead, they should appear fair to every student.

- **Causes originating with the school:** The Physical conditions of the school should help provide such healthy and suitable classroom conditions that will contribute effectively to making the teaching-learning process a successful one. For instance, Gillean (2014) emphasizes that an over-crowded classroom in which there is insufficient space for students to carry out practical activities, or in which the arrangement of seating may prevent students from following the teacher's work, may hinder the learning process and cause undesirable behavior. Moreover, students should be familiarized with the school rules by contributing to the establishment of these regulations, the purpose being to know their rights and duties as well as the restrictions and limits of their behaviors inside the school. Like this, they will know the obligations of good conduct in the school and become aware of the consequences of their acts. In this respect, Coulby and Harper (1985) argue that "the rules need to be known to pupils and be discussed with them...the aim of rules after all is not to inspire blind obedience, but rather to develop in children and the young qualities of self-discipline and cooperation" (p.137). Further, there are so many other problems that might be attributed to the curriculum in terms of its quantity and quality. According to Fontana (1988), a good curriculum is that which is perceived by the students as being of value to them and their future. That is, a curriculum that teaches them useful information and skills which help them grow and develop while preparing for their future. Finally, Cooper (2011) states that schools with discipline problems are usually those schools where the rules are not clear, fair, and firmly enforced, where there is poor teacher-administration cooperation or with inactive administrations, or large and overcrowded schools that lack resources needed for teaching.

- **Causes originating with the home, the community, and the larger social order:** There are plenty of possible sources of problem behavior that can be traced back to the society. To mention but a few, absence of family love, negative parental attitude toward school and education, disharmony in the home environment, bad/poor home environment, child abuse problems, poverty, negative neighborhood environment, violence or inappropriate behavior portrayed on TV, in movies, internet and in popular music, availability of weapons, racial tension etc. In line with this, Elias et al. (2009), who conducted a study involving 113 at risk students in 25 secondary schools in Malaysia, found that most of these students' misbehavior originate from family problems such as lack of parental monitoring, broken connections in the family and problems associated with poverty.

It is worth mentioning that problem behavior is also related to its antecedent. Brown (2012) identified the causes of misbehavior in the classroom by its antecedents. Antecedents are the conditions that immediately precede the occurrence of the student's misbehavior (Hieneman et al., 1999; O'Neill et al., 1997). Antecedents include the specific times of day,

settings, people, and activities that either occur or are present before the student exhibits challenging behavior. For example, frustration can be the result of a family problem, response ignorance by the teacher, a complex material, or lack of functional vocabulary to communication, or pace of activity... Thus, it is very critical for teachers to know under what conditions a certain behavior occurs, what antecedents precede the behavior, and what consequences follow the occurrence of that behavior in order to deal with it effectively.

In an attempt to investigate the factors behind disruptive behavior in the Moroccan high school classroom, Benaissi (2021) found that the sources of these behavior problems were related to: 1) Students (their age, their attitude toward the school, and their level of language proficiency, 2) the teaching context, and 3) the family context. Benaissi (2021) concluded that one of the main factors related to the student are attributed to adolescence. Besides, other disruptive behaviors among students were motivated by the attempt to attract the attention of the teacher and their peers. Moreover, other reasons stem from taking up bad habits, mainly drugs, which usually accompany the adolescence period. In addition, students' difficulties with learning such as lack of concentration and low level of proficiency, are direct outcomes of the students' poor ability to cope with the lesson, which usually push the student to engage in problem behavior. Furthermore, other sources of misbehavior include the student's negative image about the school, teachers, and the school subjects, bad rapport with teachers. More interestingly, students' misbehavior can also be traced back to the teachers themselves (Aliakbari & Bozorgmanesh, 2015). For instance, teachers' sticking to the textbook and teaching to it all the time creates monotony, introduces boredom into the classroom, stirs students' feeling of neglect coupled with teachers' unfairness as other causes of problem behavior.

All in all, along with its negative effect on the quality of the teaching-learning process, problem behavior also results in school dropout, teacher stress, poor self-efficacy and burnout and retention, which lead teachers who fail to handle problem behaviors effectively to consider resigning from their profession (Brown, 2012; Carson & MacGregor, 2014; Chang, 2013; Hong, 2012). This is why it is important for all teachers to stay up-to-date with regard to effective strategies and ways of managing their students' problem behaviors.

D. Managing students' misbehavior

An effective management of problem behavior necessitates the presence of a classroom management plan that can provide teachers with appropriate and effective techniques which will help them to deal with any sort of student disruptive behavior that can occur in the classroom. The information provided below relates to two approaches of dealing with misbehaviors. Each approach comprises a

number of management principles. While the first constitutes a preventive approach to disciplinary problems, the second is meant as a supportive and corrective approach to disciplinary problems. Such a plan, if implemented appropriately, could make students more respectful of others, more responsible for their learning, and above all more effective in their practice of self-control.

• **A preventive approach to disciplinary problems**

Obviously, the most effective way of managing misbehaviors is the one preventing their occurrence in the first place. Cahrlton and David (1994) state that the best response to disruptive behaviors is preventing them from the beginning. Listed below are five principles that can help teachers prevent the occurrence of misbehaviors in their classrooms:

➤ **Principle 1: Assess, clarify, and communicate needs and expectations**

Student and teacher needs, rights, and expectations should be openly discussed on the first day of class and reviewed periodically as a preventive measure. Indeed, students' basic needs include survival, belonging, power, fun, and freedom. They have the right to learn without being disrupted by others. They expect the teacher to facilitate that learning by setting limits on disruptive student behavior. On their part, teachers need the full attention of each student. They have the right to establish optimal learning environments. They may expect behavior which contributes to optimal student growth. That's why the student is expected to come prepared to class with appropriate class materials and a willingness to learn. They are expected to behave respectfully towards the teacher and their classmates alike. Furthermore, the student is expected to accept the consequences of misbehavior. As for the teachers, they are expected to consider interesting curricula which meet the students' needs, to provide stimulating and useful lessons, and to always ask the students to be the best they can be. Furthermore, teachers are expected to use teaching practices which could motivate students to engage in worthwhile learning activities (Alhassan, 2002).

➤ **Principle 2: Create a warm and nurturing classroom atmosphere**

The classroom should be a place where a student feels welcome and at home. Students need to feel safe and accepted, thus ridicule and sarcasm are not allowed. Mutual respect is the key for maintaining this climate. Regarding the physical environment, the classroom should be clean and pleasantly decorated with student creations, yet free from distracting stimuli. The desks should be arranged to allow students to work cooperatively as well as allowing the teacher to circulate freely and efficiently. Feedback also plays a strong role in learning. Teachers' constructive responses to students' output help in providing a learning space in which students' efforts are appreciated and valued. Moreover, as regards the rapport with

students, each student deserves to be treated with dignity and respect. Students should be personally greeted at the door. They should be given as much personal attention as possible during and outside of class. Furthermore, a teacher's enthusiasm, level of concern for the students, and class involvement all can affect the level of class togetherness. This force can benefit cooperative learning exercises, and make the curricula seem much more enjoyable (Childs, 2014).

➤ **Principle 3: Democratically develop a set of rules and consequences**

Teachers and students must work together to establish a classroom charter after negotiating discipline plans and classroom rules that could come with clear and effective effects. The rules should be agreed upon and understood by everyone in the class. It should be understood from the outset that when rules are broken, consequences will be applied fairly and consistently. To illustrate this, the teacher solicits help to create a set of classroom rules and responsibilities by involving the students in passing the classroom regulations of conduct. The ideal list would be short and reflect the concepts of mutual respect and personal responsibility. Coulby and Harper (1985) state that "the rules need to be known to pupils and be discussed with them...the aim of rules after all is not to inspire blind obedience, but rather to develop in children and young qualities of self-discipline and cooperation" (p.137). Besides, logical consequences or the results which consistently follow certain behaviors should be explained in advance and agreed to by the students. It is by understanding the consequences of disruptive behavior, that students will make better choices. Consequences should be related to the misbehavior so the students can see the connection. Once the class has developed its list of rules, they should be displayed as a reminder to those who may wish to break them. This gives the teacher something to refer to and point at when requesting certain behavior to stop.

➤ **Principle 4: Develop a daily routine, but at the same time remain flexible**

Students will often misbehave if they do not know exactly what they should do and when. Teachers can avoid this dilemma by installing class routines and procedures, which allow the student to begin and complete work expeditiously. Since every minute of students' instruction time counts, as part of an effective routine, it is best for students to begin work immediately after the bell rings. Further, part of the class time should be spent covering the daily lesson. During this time, it is understood that only one person speaks at a time. Students who have questions are encouraged to raise their hands to ask them. Once the lesson has been presented, and all questions have been answered, the students are allowed to work cooperatively on their assignment. Once the lesson

has been presented, the teacher is free to answer individual student questions. During this time, the teacher must be aware of what is happening in all parts of the classroom while monitoring students' work. Finally, since lesson plans can be affected by conditions beyond the control of the teacher, there may be cases where class activities must be restructured or rescheduled to accommodate the changed conditions (Carson & Matthews, 2014).

➤ **Principle 5: Be alert to problem behavior transfer**

Since students take many school subjects, it is important for teachers to be aware that students can transfer different types of behavior from one class to another. That is the reason why it is necessary for teachers to make their students realize that each teacher has specific expectations of the disciplinary routine to administrate in their classrooms. For instance, when students enjoy "a show" of disruptive behavior with a teacher, they usually expect the next session to involve the same amount of fun. One way to handle this is to use warm-ups such as engaging them in short discussions. The objective being to offer a smooth transition to the teacher's own session and to absorb the intention to reproduce the misbehaviors tolerated in other classes (Benaissi, 2021).

➤ **Principle 6: Make learning more attractive and fun for the student**

Schools exist for the students, and not for the teachers. It is important for the teacher to try their best to make the curriculum relevant, the lessons interesting, and the activities enjoyable. The result will be an engaged and active participant in the learning process. Besides, students respond well to the anticipation of preferred cooperative and group activities. They act as incentives. It is possible to get an entire class on task if the incentive is available to all students, and attractive to the entire group so as to merit extra effort. The incentive should be both stimulating to the students, and educationally valuable. In addition, the teacher can make learning more attractive by giving a coherent and smoothly paced lesson presentation. Getting the lesson going, keeping it going with smooth transitions, avoiding pauses or abrupt changes that interfere with student activity, and postponing satiation are important in maintaining positive student behavior associated with being on task. Further, teachers should vary the way they present their lessons from day to day. They may demonstrate, lead a group activity or discussion, or have students work quietly on their own. Routines can become ruts if there is not some variety to spice things up. Finally, lesson topics should be relevant to the students if at all possible. Teaching strategies should be harmonious with student learning styles. The teacher should help the students develop learning goals which are real, attainable, and a source of pride. Activities should

be fun for the students. These raise in students the ability to link success with hard work and good behavior. They also help to integrate low achievers by seizing any learning moment to make them experience success (Benaissi, 2021).

• **A supportive and corrective approach towards disciplinary problems**

Misbehavior remains an unpredictable problem that is likely to occur in all conditions. However, no matter what the reason is for students' misbehavior, teachers need to respond to it effectively. The following principles provide teachers with effective strategies for dealing with students' disruptive behaviors:

➤ **Principle 1: Deal with misbehavior, quickly, consistently, and respectfully**

Misbehavior is a disruption to the effectiveness of a teacher. The time spent dealing with misbehaving would be better spent teaching the students. Therefore, misbehavior should be dealt with quickly and consistently with class defined consequences. Non-verbal communication such as body language, facial expressions, gestures, eye contact, and physical proximity can all be effective in promoting self-control by the student. It is important that a teacher is aware enough to be able to recognize when misbehavior may occur, and to have non-verbal methods to prevent escalation. Also, it is possible that a verbal reminder of the classroom rules and consequences will be all that is necessary to stop a student misbehavior. Another technique is redirecting behavior. That is, upon an act of misbehavior, a teacher may describe the action to the student and suggest an acceptable alternative action. The student usually only has to be reminded of what he is supposed to be doing. For example, "Instead of using that phone, I would like you to work on your assignment for the next five minutes. You can use your phone when the session is over." Moreover, in dealing with attention-seeking students, if a teacher ignores an attention seeking student, the misbehavior usually escalates to a level which eventually cannot be ignored (Arbuckle & Little, 2004). Therefore, it is best if the teacher can redirect the student's behavior, and attempt to give the student attention when he is not demanding it. This method encourages students to seek motivation from within, instead of depending on attention from without. Besides, it is important that the teacher, as an authority figure in the classroom, not engage in power struggles with students. It is best to redirect a power-seeking student's behavior by offering some position of responsibility or decision making. More importantly, teachers should address the behavior, not the character of the student. The teacher has the power to build or destroy student self-concept and personal relationships. Good communication addresses the situation directly, letting the student decide whether their behavior is consistent with what they expect of themselves.

Yet, to be effective, consequences must be applied consistently. They should never be harmful physically and psychologically to the student. When they are invoked, the student should understand that they have chosen them by misbehaving. Sometimes, students are unwilling to listen to the teacher. At this point, a teacher can help prevent misbehavior from escalating by talking with and listening to the student privately, and rationally discuss the problem behavior. The privacy enhances the possibility for a constructive discussion. Confrontation with an unwilling student could make the teacher appear weak in front of the class (Arbuckle & Little, 2004).

➤ **Principle 2: When all else fails, respectfully remove the student from the class**

Continued disruptions should not be tolerated in the classroom. They are detrimental to the overall objective that all students will become active and effective learners. Therefore, such students should be respectfully removed from class, and dealt with unconventionally. If a student does not accept the consequence of breaking a class rule, then he or she should not be allowed to remain in the class until the consequence is accepted. This should be made clear to the students from day one, and should be strictly enforced with the administration's approval and consent of course. Moreover, a teacher may request a one-on-one meeting with the student to discuss a specific problem behavior. The goal of this meeting is to gain insight so that helpful guidance may be provided. For more serious behavioral matters, the teacher may also request a meeting with the student's parent for the same purpose. Another technique is to set a behavior plan for the misbehaving student. This plan is for students who do not respond to conventional discipline. The plan can be written in a contract form, and should include expected behaviors for the student, positive recognition for compliance, and consequences for failing. The plan should address one or two significant problems at a time, and should use consequences which differ from the previously failed ones used by the rest of the class (Thomson, 2009).

To sum up, as types and frequency of misbehavior seem to be an indication of the displeasure students and teachers experience (Maughan, 2001), it is important for teachers to be equipped with effective techniques and strategies to prevent and cope with these problems. Accordingly, this study attempted to address three specific research questions:

- What are the most frequent types of discipline problems teachers face in Moroccan EFL high school classes?
- What are the major reasons behind disciplinary problems in Moroccan EFL high school classes?
- How can Moroccan high school teachers of English manage their classrooms successfully?

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research design

The issue of problem behavior in the Moroccan EFL high school classroom has been investigated using a mixed-methods design – whereby data is collected via quantitative and qualitative research instruments. The aim is twofold: first, to identify the different types of disciplinary problems in Moroccan EFL high school classes; second, to investigate the sources of problem behavior in Moroccan EFL high school classes, and ultimately suggest effective strategies to deal with them.

B. Participants

The participants totaled 359 including both teachers and students. More specifically, the study involved 69 public high school English teachers and 240 public high school students. Of the 10 teachers interviewed, five were observed before being interviewed. Demographically, the EFL teachers involved in this study were diverse in terms of gender, age, academic degree, place of work, academic background, seniority, and professional experience. The teachers came from different backgrounds and from various regions of Morocco (Rabat-Salé-Kénitra, Sous-Mass, Drâa-Tafilalet, Guelmim-Oued Noun & Rabat sale). The students were also diverse in terms of age (15-21), gender, grade (Common Core, Baccalaureate 1st year, and Baccalaureate 2nd year), school (Charif Idrissi & Abdellah Gennoun); and major (SVT, Physics, Mathematics A, Mathematics B, Arts and Humanities).

C. Sampling procedure

The sampling procedure envisaged for this study is that of convenience sampling. Thus, participants in this study were EFL teachers and students who were included based on what was available and accessible to the researcher. Some teachers were invited for follow-up interviews based on their responses to the questionnaires. All participants were informed of the value of their participation before being interviewed, observed, and questioned to ensure their consent to participate in the study. Moreover, participants were assured of the confidentiality of the information they provided.

D. Data collection

The instruments utilized in this study included a questionnaire for students, another questionnaire for teachers, interviews with both teachers and students, and classroom observations. As postulated by Richards (2012), the integration of several methods and points of view develops a kind of dialogue between different ways of seeing, interpreting, and knowing. Regarding the questionnaires, in addition to the basic information, the questionnaire included 15 statements pertaining to the issue of problem behavior. Closed questions used a Likert scale. The questionnaires also included 5 open-ended questions allowing respondents to give their opinion and make suggestions. The student questionnaire has been written in Arabic to ensure students' understanding of the questionnaire items and, therefore, the reliability of the answers. As for the class observations, they took place at the Charif Idrissi high school in Rabat. Face-to-face interviews were conducted with teachers working in Rabat and online interviews with teachers teaching in other cities. Student interviews were held with students from Charif Idrissi high school and Abdellah Gennoun high school in Rabat.

E. Data Analysis

The analysis of the data collected for this research was done both quantitatively by using scores and percentages displayed in graphs and qualitatively by interpreting and commenting on the data collected.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. The types and frequency of student misbehavior in Moroccan EFL High School Classes

The first question administered to the teachers was: "How often do you encounter disruptive behaviors in your classes?" To that question, as can be seen in figure 1, most teachers answered "sometimes" while an important portion of them answered "usually". This shows that the majority of high school teachers of English still face problem behavior as one of the biggest challenges to the effectiveness of the teaching and learning in their classes.

Fig. 1: Frequency of student misbehavior in Moroccan EFL high school classes

The findings regarding the types of student misbehavior in the Moroccan EFL high school classes reveal that there are six main misbehavior types teachers tackle with. As figure 2 clearly illustrates, most of those misbehavior types are minor disciplinary problems.

Fig. 2: Types of disciplinary problems in Moroccan EFL high school classrooms

Moreover, there are many types of disciplinary problems in Moroccan EFL high school classrooms the researcher either observed or deduced from interviews with the teachers as well as with the students. This variety of problems can be grouped into three different categories:

a) Minor Disciplinary Problems

As shown in figure 2, this category includes the most frequent disruptive behaviors that Moroccan EFL high school teachers face on almost a daily basis. Problems of this kind include some behaviors which teachers can ignore or make a brief comment to correct. Examples which go under this category are:

a. Late Arrival to Classes

Late arrival to class is one of the most common problems that the majority of Moroccan teachers suffer from, more particularly Moroccan EFL high school teachers. Interviewed teachers reported that students come late to class usually after the break time or if the session starts at eight in the morning. Such behavior can be tolerated, but if it is repeated many times from the same students, teachers would try first to know the reason behind these students coming late. If there is no acceptable reason, then they either not accept the late comers or send them to the administration.

b. Absenteeism

Absenteeism is also a major problem that, not only Moroccan EFL high school teachers suffer from, but teachers all around Morocco in general. Students may suffer from serious health or family problems that prevent them from attending certain classes. Others, on the other hand, skip class because they either underestimate the English subject with regard to its coefficient or because of a conflict with the teacher of English, or also because of their poor level in the English language.

c. Making unnecessary Noises and Unauthorized Talking in the

Classroom: It is true that adolescents always have so many things to say and to tell each other. Moroccan EFL high school teachers usually tolerate some light chatting in class especially during pair or group work activities. However, most Moroccan EFL high school teachers interviewed said that they cannot accept students chatting while they are explaining the lesson or giving instructions.

d. Passing each other Notes in Class

Moroccan High school students resort to passing notes to each other, especially when they are deprived from chatting. The majority of Moroccan high school teachers of English do not like this kind of behavior in class because it can distract the teachers' and students' attention alike.

- e. **Lying to the Teacher**
Most Moroccan high school students lie to their teachers when they do not do the homework, when they tempt to cheat, or when they miss classes for no reason. Most of the teachers interviewed said that they usually put up with students' lies.
- f. **Not Doing Homework**
According to students' answers in the questionnaire, the majority of them usually come to the classroom without doing their homework. The interviewed teachers confirmed this by reporting that this issue happens regularly to them. Some teachers suggest a technique they found very useful. It involves reinforcing the positive behavior. That is, teachers give extra points or bonuses to those who do their homework.
- g. **Inattention during Class Activities and Non-Participation**
Sometimes, students show a kind of unwillingness to participate actively in specific class activities. Most of the teachers reported that it is due to lack of interest in the English subject or to their poor level in the language. Some other teachers mentioned that they have less disciplinary problems with Maths-majoring students compared with students majoring in Arts and Human sciences. In fact, teachers reported having most of the behavior problems with students whose major is Human Sciences. This indicates that the level of students in the language plays an important role in predicting the occurrence of disruptive behavior. Therefore, the role of the teacher is to involve them by knowing their interests and trying to fulfill them using different activities that match their levels.
- h. **Unauthorized Mobile Phone use in Class**
During the classroom observations period, it was noticed that some students use cell phones inside the classroom especially during group or pair work activities. Moreover, most interviewed teachers said they took serious measures with students who use cell phones during activities or whose cell phones beep or ring while they are explaining. What is more, most teachers seem to agree that the teacher should set a model himself or herself as regards using the mobile phone so that any measure taken against students would seem fair to them.
- i. **Making the Rest of the Class Laugh**
This type of disciplinary problems is also called "Clowning". It is common in Moroccan EFL high school classes. Students who exhibit this kind of behavior are usually seeking attention or a refuge to combat boredom and monotony. Some of the teachers interviewed said that sometimes they can join students laughing about the situation then bring students back to the lesson or activity in hand. But sometimes, other teachers declared that it is necessary to respond strictly to this kind of behavior especially if the student is exhibiting the behavior at the expense of other students or the teacher himself.
- b) **Serious Disciplinary Problems**
Grouped under this category are all the different kinds of disciplinary problems that seem somehow challenging to the majority of Moroccan EFL high school teachers. When asked about their reaction to such behavior, most teachers said that they would kick the student out of the classroom or call for the administration's help. Many of them said that such behaviors may threaten other students' security and their own security if not dealt with properly. Disciplinary problems of this kind include:
- a. **Cheating in Exams**
Copying other students' answers during tests and exams or cheating in general is also one of the major problems that Moroccan EFL high school teachers suffer from. Oftentimes, teachers can stop students from copying in tests by some light punishments, such as, reducing their test mark or preventing them from finishing the exam. But at times teachers tend to resort to more serious punishments especially if students try to defy the teacher.
- b. **Verbal Violence Aimed at Students**
Sometimes, students engage in disputes and verbally assault their classmates. The majority of the interviewed teachers said that they do not allow such disrespectful behaviors towards students because this violates class discipline rules. They usually take strict measures to put an end to this kind of behavior and, most of the times send students who exhibit such behavior to the administration.
- c. **Damaging Class Properties**
This behavior is referred to as "Vandalism". Unfortunately, most Moroccan high school students develop the tendency of damaging school properties. During the observation period in the two high schools, the researcher did not witness students damage school properties; yet from the school and the classroom conditions, it is clear that damaging class property is a habit in Moroccan high schools. Such behaviors include damaging the door locks, writing obscene words and expressions on the walls, the desks and the board, breaking windowpane glass, carving names and graffiti on desks, boards and walls. Most of the interviewed teachers said that these kinds of behavior require the administration's intervention because teachers alone cannot deal with them. Teachers,

thus, request the necessary measures on the part of the administration against students who are caught red-handed damaging the school properties.

- d. **Using Abusive Language Inside the Classroom**
This kind of misbehavior was noticed frequently during the observation period especially among students. One of the teachers ignored a student's abusive language who gave an indecent example when asked to answer a question. The teacher only corrected the students' word with another decent word and explained why he should not have used such language inside the classroom. When occurred for the second time, however, the teacher's reaction was different and more serious because he felt that the student who uttered a very indecent expression meant to hurt one of his classmates. The teacher immediately stopped the student and warned him that if such behavior is repeated he would take severe measures against him. Moreover, teachers' answers in the questionnaires indicate that students usually answer them rudely when they comment on their students' inappropriate behavior or ask them to participate in a class activity. Most of the teachers said that they sometimes send these students to the administration or demand the presence of their parents, they even dispel these students from class for a limited period of time in order to ensure and regain respect in front of their students as way to prevent the re-occurrence of such behavior.
- e. **Bullying**
Although bullying is not very common in Moroccan high schools, it is a serious problem as it can dramatically affect the ability of students to progress academically and socially. All the teachers interviewed also declared that they are aware of the seriousness of the problem. That is why, they always express the need for a comprehensive plan that would involve students, parents, and school staff to ensure that all students can learn in a safe and fear-free environment.
- f. **Forging Parents' Signature**
Though it rarely occurred, forging parents' signature can be a big problem for the teacher, the school administration, and the students themselves. This kind of disciplinary problem is deemed by most teachers a very serious one. Students usually forge their parents' signature in some administrative school documents such as documents of parental permission to school trips and excursions or grade reports to be signed by parents. They also do this more frequently with register or the absence sheets as they call them so that the administration would

not notify their parents about their being absent. This kind of behavior seems more serious if seen from a long-term legal perspective. Indeed, if not dealt with properly, and if students were not sensitized to the danger of such behavior, they can take it for granted and develop this kind of behavior as they grow up, and this would become even a social problem. All the interviewed teachers agreed on the fact that they can never tolerate such problem behavior, they either reprimand students in private and sensitize them about the seriousness of the matter or take things forward by talking with their parents.

- c) **Severe Disciplinary Problems**
The misbehaviors included in this category are very serious and challenging. Teachers need to try to address them carefully and with the right sanctions. To respond to this kind of disciplinary problems, Moroccan EFL high school teachers usually call for the administration's help or even the authorities' help like the police. Examples of this type of disciplinary problems are:
 - a. **Physical Violence Aimed at other Students**
This type of disciplinary problems happened twice during the observation period. The teachers interviewed said that students who physically harm their peers were usually expelled from school for a limited period of time. Some were even sent to the police in case of serious consequences of such physical violence. Most of the teachers also said that they never interfere in such problems. They only call for the help of the administration which takes the necessary measures.
 - b. **Physical Violence Aimed at the Teacher**
The teachers' answers in the questionnaires indicate that this type of discipline problems is very rare. Moreover, none of the interviewed teachers reported to have experienced such kind of misbehavior. Yet, some of the teachers reported similar problems that happened to their colleagues. These were mostly instances that happened while teachers invigilate Baccalaureate exams. One of these teachers was threatened and then physically attacked by a troublesome student because the teacher prevented him from cheating in the exam. The teachers called for the administration help and the student was then taken out. The student was not let to take the rest of the Baccalaureate exam, and thus failed the exam and repeated the year. The teachers went to the police to report what happened. The student was arrested in the afternoon by the police and signed a written promise not to threaten the teachers again.

B. The Main Reasons Behind Disciplinary Problems

When asked "In your opinion, what are the main causes behind disciplinary problems?", the majority of Moroccan EFL high school teachers stated that the main causes of problem behavior are those originating from students themselves (social, psychological and physical factors...) and from the school (physical conditions, school rules,

curriculum...). While, very few of them stated that disciplinary problems result mainly from the teacher (See figure 3). This implies that the majority of Moroccan EFL high school teachers are not aware of a very important portion of problem behavior causes. That is, the causes originating from them as teachers (lack of competence, fairness, punctuality, poor planning...).

Fig. 3: The Main Causes Behind Disciplinary Problems in the Moroccan EFL high school classroom

In sorting out the causes of disciplinary problems, the data collected through interviews with high school teachers and students can be grouped into three categories as follows:

a) External Factors

External factors refer to the factors that push students to misbehave, but which are neither related to the teachers' attitudes, the lesson type, nor the classroom atmosphere, but are more related to students' personal, home, and former education. Such factors include:

a. Education

Education is one of the major external factors that push students to misbehave in the classroom. Students' previous education can affect students' present behavior in class. In this regard, Moroccan high school students tend to be influenced by what they experienced before with other teachers. Hence, students' expectations of the learning experience can be colored either by unpleasant memories or by what they were allowed to get away with.

b. Family

In addition to the students' education impact on their behaviors, family background and atmosphere can also play an important role in shaping students' behaviors (Tony & Kenneth, 1994). Some family problems, like divorce, parents' emotional and physical absence, or parents' negative attitudes, may lead students to lack attention in the classroom, isolation, aggressive behaviors towards peers and teachers, damaging and attacking attitude, use of drugs, and lack of interest in education as a whole. Thus, misbehaving in class is a normal reaction to this kind of a student's life conditions. Some of the interviewed students said that they cannot stand family problems, especially parents' continuous disputes. As a result, they resort to taking drugs, or creating problems to other students whom they envy because they have no problems. Moreover, parents' attitudes towards English, or to learning in general, or even teachers themselves can predispose students to misbehave in class, because they do not care. Many of the interviewed students said that English is a secondary subject where they can enjoy their time without being obliged to work hard. In addition,

many students said that this is what their parents usually tell them; they ask them to focus more on science subjects and not waste time doing English homework.

c. Other External Factors

Other external factors that cause students to misbehave inside the classroom and that many of the interviewed students pointed at are:

- Noise coming from outside the classroom: when students see their friends out of the window or hear other students' noise, they can be easily distracted from the lesson. This is normal because they cannot concentrate on two things at the same time. Most of them prefer to follow what is going on outside the classroom than following what is going on inside it.
- The weather: relatively extreme weather conditions may cause students to lose their motivation and focus in class. Students stated that if the weather is too hot or too cold they feel too relaxed or too nervy and this prevents them from being attentive.
- Tiredness: almost all high school students show reluctance to participate and concentrate on classroom activities if they are tired. Students may be tired of additional effort they had made in previous sessions of the day. Teachers said that neither students nor teachers like the last sessions of the day because they both feel unable to carry on teaching and learning.

b) Internal Factors

Internal factors designate the factors that push students to misbehave inside the classroom. These include:

a. Boredom

Boredom is one of the most important internal factors that lead to students' disruptive behavior in the classroom. Indeed, some studies have found that boredom prevailing in some teaching contexts can be the main reason for students' misbehavior (Fallis & Opotow, 2003; Mc Giboney & Carter, 1988). During the observation period, it was noticed that when students are engaged in a task or a topic they are unlikely to misbehave, but they misbehave more when they lose interest. Accordingly, boredom stems from students' disengagement in a task which may be due to their lack of interest in certain activities, because they are too challenging or too easy.

b. Scratching Students' Self-Esteem

Protecting students' self-esteem is very important to insure classroom order and discipline (Gillean, 2014). Students may feel that their self-esteem is scratched if they feel a lack of respect from the teacher or from peers, or when they are asked to do a task which they feel unable to fulfill. These may result in students' frustration and may make disruptive behavior a natural reaction to protect

their self-esteem. For some students, by shouting in class, responding rudely to the teacher, or abusing their peers verbally, they try to impress peers and force the teacher to take them seriously.

c. Avoiding Inadequacy

According to the interviewed teachers, avoiding inadequacy is a very common cause of disciplinary problems in class. In fact, adolescents misbehave when they would rather appear "bad" than appear inadequate in some way. For example, if a class assignment is too difficult, the student may choose to intentionally misbehave and be sent out of the class to avoid having to participate and look inferior. Sometimes, it is a matter of perfectionism, where the student may misbehave if they know they will not be the best at a task.

d. Teachers' Attitudes

Problem behavior has been widely discussed by considering the students and their environment, and some external factors as the main causes of disciplinary problems in the classroom. Yet, teachers' attitudes can be to a greater extent the primary cause of students' misbehavior in class (Shamnadh & Anzari, 2019). Stephens and Crawley (1994) state that problem behavior is triggered by the teacher more than by the student. For instance, when teachers are unfair in the classroom, favor hard-working students over low achievers, or appear unapproachable and unprofessional, students are likely to misbehave as a kind of revenge on that teacher. Also, misbehavior is more likely to occur when the teacher is not motivated and the classroom environment is not conducive to learning (Shamnadh & Anzari, 2019). More than that, a lot depends on how teachers behave in class, especially when problem behavior first takes place. As mentioned earlier, students who feel their self-esteem to have been damaged by the way the teacher disciplined them, are more likely to behave badly in the future. On the contrary, teachers who respond effectively to disciplinary problems without damaging students' self-esteem are more likely to be successful in stopping students from misbehaving. Sometimes this can only be done by ignoring the behavior.

C. *Effective Strategies to Cope with Problem Behavior*

a) Preventing the Occurance of Disciplinary Problems

When asked "What particular strategies have you found to be most effective in managing your classroom?" Most Moroccan high school teachers of English agreed on the fact that the most effective way to manage problem behavior is seeking to prevent its occurrence altogether. Here are some ideas:

- **Building a Healthy Teacher-Student Rapport**

From the information provided by the interviewed teachers, it can be concluded that good teaching methods as well as a good teacher-student rapport help in preventing problem behavior. Moreover, in their teaching methods, teachers should take into consideration that each class is a mixed ability class. Accordingly, teachers have to create a flexible method of teaching adapted to every class requirements. Gaining students' interests and enhancing their motivation in class is a crucial way to prevent problem behavior. Similarly, a good relationship between students and teachers helps in avoiding problem behavior. Teachers should show professionalism and serve as good models to their students. Generally speaking, students respect teachers who prove to be competent, motivated, and well organized. Professionalism is also about practicing what a teacher preaches (Cooper, 2011). In order to avoid the problem of having students coming late to class for example, teachers should be punctual themselves. Moreover, a good rapport between teachers and students is of utmost importance in preventing problem behavior. Teachers would show love to every student, engage everyone in the classroom, show respect to every point of view, and respect the student talking time. Teachers generally should create a socio-affective relationship with their students, as it is an effective way to avoid disciplinary problems.

- **Creating a Code of Conduct**

Another way to prevent problem behavior in the classroom used by many of the interviewed teachers is creating a code of conduct. The interviewed teachers agreed that it is an effective way of preventing problem behavior as it shows to students where they stand from the beginning of the year. More importantly, students should be involved in creating their own code of conduct. The teacher should negotiate with students the rules and also the effects of violating each rule that should be included in their own code of conduct. By doing so, students would feel responsible towards assuring the non-violation of any rule, and when they know they have violated one of the rules of conduct they can already predict the consequences. It is also useful to hang a hard copy of the code of conduct on the classroom walls so that students can refer to it on a daily basis.

b) **Correcting Misbehaviors**

On the other hand, misbehavior remains an uncontrolled problem that is likely to occur in all conditions no matter how hard teachers work to prevent it (Backes et al., 2003). Therefore, only appropriate responses would prevent the future occurrence of disciplinary problems. Accordingly, from the interviews held with a group of Moroccan EFL high school teachers, and with a group of Moroccan high school students, a variety of tentative

classroom management techniques and strategies for dealing with misbehavior effectively are suggested.

- **Preserve Students' Dignity**

As mentioned earlier, students' self-esteem is of paramount importance in predicting problem behavior. Particularly, adolescent students would go to extreme lengths to save face in front of their classmates. That's why, teachers should try to avoid dealing with misbehavior in front of the students as that may cause students to be embarrassed or humiliated. Moreover, teachers may develop some habits of dealing appropriately with disruptive students such as giving students a chance to assume some responsibility for correcting their own misbehavior, especially if teachers have already established a code of conduct. For example, the teacher may ask "what do you think we can do about this situation?". By doing so, students assume responsibility for their behaviors. Teachers can also make sure to distinguish students' character from their behavior. An example of this can be, instead of saying "you are lazy" say "You haven't done your homework". By doing so, the teacher judges the behavior not the person. Finally, it is best for teachers to speak with disruptive students calmly and quietly, even privately if possible.

- **Consider the Context to Determine if it is a Misbehavior or Not**

The context is what determines whether a particular action is to be considered as misbehavior or not. There are some misbehaviors which may be tolerated in some cases. For example, in some classes, wearing a hat and sitting on a desk are perfectly acceptable. However, in others, they are not. Accordingly, when defining misbehavior, teachers should take into consideration whether the behavior violates established rules, whether it is disrupting the normal flow of instructional activities, and whether it is harmful to the teacher or other students. Otherwise, it may not be necessary to intervene.

- **Keep the Flow of Instruction Going with a Minimum of Distraction**

Teacher's main job is to teach, and they cannot do so if students' behavior is distracting or disruptive. But sometimes, teachers' disciplinary interventions may be so loud, intrusive, and long-winded that they waste more time than the initial problem. In order to avoid this situation, teachers should learn to anticipate potential problems and head them off. Then, if it is necessary to intervene, it is better to be as short as possible so that teaching and learning would not be interrupted.

- **Match the Discipline Strategy with the Misbehavior**

Teachers should make sure that their discipline strategy suits the misbehavior. In fact, an effective teacher would not severely punish a student for whispering, just as he/she would not express mild disappointment if a student rips up a peer's copybook. For instance, while dealing with minor disciplinary problems, all what is needed is to just give "the look" while moving closer to the student exhibiting problem behavior. Many teachers also make use of facial expressions, eye contact, or gestures like hand signals which can prove quite effective. In general, teachers can use a hierarchy of consequences, that is, using a set of responses that build in terms of seriousness and severity. This way, they can respond to a particular behavior effectively based on its degree of seriousness.

- **Use Verbal Interventions**

Sometimes, verbal interventions are necessary, such as directing a student to the task at hand. Or if the misbehavior occurs while a group discussion is going on, calling on a student to answer a question may draw them back in. Sometimes, it is also more effective to use a nondirective verbal intervention, such as saying the student's name. This prompts the appropriate behavior while leaving to the misbehaving student the responsibility of figuring out what to do.

- **Enforce the Consequence**

Sometimes, teachers find it necessary to enforce a consequence, especially when nonverbal cues or verbal reminders are not enough. Most of the teachers interviewed choose to discuss consequences of particular misbehavior when rules and procedures are taught, so students are aware, right from the beginning, of the consequences of violating a rule. Generally, teachers' consequences fall into the following categories: deducting some marks from their exam grades, exclusion from the group, loss of privileges, private meetings, and contacting parents.

- **Ignore It**

There are times when it may be appropriate to ignore the misbehavior if intervention is going to only obstruct the flow of the lesson. For example, during a discussion, a student may be so eager to participate that he/she forgets to raise his/her hand, or someone becomes momentarily distracted and inattentive, or two students quietly exchange a comment while the teacher is explaining or giving directions to the whole class. In cases like these, an intervention can be more disruptive than the student's behavior. However, teachers should be cautious when using this technique. Ignoring minor disciplinary problems may indicate to students that teachers are unaware of what is going on. Therefore, teachers should keep in mind that the

main goal is to deal with misbehavior in the least disruptive way possible.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

All in all, the majority of Moroccan EFL high school teachers who constituted this research population seem to be aware of the hazardous phenomenon of problem behavior. Moreover, most of those teachers also use effective classroom management strategies and respond appropriately to their students' disciplinary problems. Moreover, many aspects previously discussed in this research were found among Moroccan high school students. Also, the categorization of the causes behind disciplinary problems was relevant to what was found in the field study. Similarly, the research findings confirm the findings in the literature presented in this research. Though not based on a Moroccan context, the examined literature showed a big similarity to problem behavior in Moroccan EFL high school classrooms in terms of aspects, causes, and teachers' attitudes. Finally, some effective responses to disciplinary problems examined in the literature seemed relevant and effective in the Moroccan context especially that some Moroccan EFL high school teachers already use those measures to assure good management in their classrooms.

VI. PEDAGOGICAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings of this study can be instructive for school administrators, teachers, prospective teachers, policy makers, curriculum developers, teacher training centers, and parents. School administrators and teachers should be aware of the different types of disciplinary problems they may encounter with their students, so that they can appropriately respond to them. In the same vein, they should cooperate to investigate the causes that push students to misbehave in their contexts. Moreover, training in preservice centers should raise prospective teachers' awareness of this problem. Besides, since teaching methods and practices can be a direct cause of misbehavior, teachers are invited to offer attractive lessons by using varied material and teaching content that cater for the different learning styles, needs, and interests of students. Furthermore, teachers should understand that there are times when students' disruptive behaviors are so deeply rooted that the use of some strategies just does not work. In cases like these, teachers should seek assistance from the administration or elsewhere. However, in most cases, using effective strategies to deal with disciplinary problems in classes helps teachers solve them effectively and help to maintain a positive and productive learning environment.

VII. LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

While interpreting the results of this study, some limitations should be kept in mind. Its scope is limited with Moroccan EFL high schools in the public sector only. Another limitation is the inability to observe many other Moroccan high schools in different cities and villages due to time constraints. Thus, further research may address the issue of problem behavior regarding the variable of gender. It may also take into consideration the setting of high

schools that is, comparing the aspects of problem behavior in prosperous and underprivileged places, between private and public high schools, or between high schools in small villages with others in big cities.

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